

Aeronautical industry in Portugal - Analysis of its influence on the economy

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ABSTRACT: The aeronautical industry in Portugal plays a significant role in the national economy, contributing to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP), generating qualified employment, and driving technological innovation.

This sector is considered strategic, as the production of technologically advanced and high value-added goods fosters scientific, technological, and economic development, while also contributing to the well-being of society.

This study aims to analyse the current state of the aeronautical industry in Portugal, its evolution over the last decade (2014–2024), future perspectives, and its impact on the national economy.

The goal is to establish a connection between the past, present, and future of the sector, that represents 1,4% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

The study includes a historical contextualization of aviation in Portugal, with a particular focus on the most recent period.

The analysis also considers the academic qualifications and diversity of professionals working in the industry, through a mixed methodological approach — both qualitative and quantitative.

To this end, a survey was conducted among aeronautical professionals in Portugal, with the purpose of gathering their perceptions regarding the future of the industry, its economic impact, the role of the State, and the integration of emerging technologies, namely Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS).

Key words: Aeronautical Industry, Portugal, Economy, UASs

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1. Introduction

This study aims to produce a valid and up-to-date study on the aeronautical industry in our country and its impact on the economy, focusing on the period from 2014 to 2024.

To this end, information is collected on the aeronautical industry to allow the study of some differentiating factors of companies, such as the geographic markets they serve, their

type of activity, their legal form or financial information, their level of competitiveness at the national and even international level, namely, how they differentiate themselves from other companies through innovation in goods, products, production methods, digital presence and intellectual property ownership; and their future expectations in Portugal.

Finally, the information obtained is organized and aggregated in order to establish a representative sample of the sector. A questionnaire on the future of the sector and the impact of the aeronautical industry in Portugal is also developed; the population and sample used for analysis will be professionals in the field.

Portugal is a reference in the history of aviation. The first flight occurred on June 20, 1540, when the shoemaker João Torto jumped from the tower of the Viseu headquarters with a device he had built himself in a failed attempt to reach the sky.

In 1709, the Portuguese priest, Bartolomeu de Gusmão, presented a revolutionary event to King João V in Lisbon, where he made a small hot air balloon rise into the air. Bartolomeu de Gusmão was then the inventor of the aerostat, thus opening the doors to aerostation and aviation.

The first Portuguese aeronaut was Abreu de Oliveira, who on May 17, 1884, rose in a gas balloon in the Ajuda reserve, eventually falling into the Tagus River near “Cais do Sodré”. Despite being a short and poorly executed flight, it gives Abreu de Oliveira the distinction of being the first Portuguese to perform an ascent in an aerostat.

One of the most important milestones in the history of Portuguese aviation was the crossing of the South Atlantic in 1922, carried out by pilots Gago Coutinho and Sacadura Cabral. It was a flight from Lisbon to Rio de Janeiro in a Fairey III, pioneering the use of a sextant adapted for air navigation, which contributed significantly to the advancement of international air navigation. (2010). History of Portuguese aviation.

2. State of the Art

The Aeronautical Industry in Portugal

The aeronautical industry in Portugal has assumed increasing importance, both for its direct impact on the economy and for its contribution to innovation and the development of technological skills in the country.

With the creation of the AED Portugal cluster (Aerospace, Defence, and Space Industries Association of Portugal) in 2016, the country consolidated its position as a strategic hub for the aerospace and defence sector.

Currently, the cluster brings together more than 150 companies, with an export capacity representing approximately 87% of its production, generating around USD \$ 1.72 billion annually. This growth not only positions Portugal as a relevant player in the global aerospace value chain but also strengthens the domestic economy by promoting the creation of skilled jobs and stimulating innovation in cutting-edge technologies (Portugal - AED Cluster Portugal Aerospace and Defence, 2024).

Among the main milestones in the development of the aeronautical industry in Portugal is the establishment of leading companies, such as Embraer in Évora City industrial

area, which have significantly contributed to the internationalization of the sector and the creation of a modern and highly qualified production infrastructure.

In addition, initiatives such as the Portugal Space 2030 program seek to expand the country's presence in the space sector, diversifying the economy and increasing the country's resilience in a competitive global economic context.

Regarding the evolution of the aeronautical industry in Portugal, it plays an important role mainly in companies such as Airbus and Embraer, especially in the production of structural components, composite materials and maintenance and repair services.

The partnership between the Portuguese aeronautical industry and Airbus highlights the importance of Portugal in global aviation and in modern commercial aircraft projects. Also of great importance is the Embraer group, which is present in Portugal through OGMA.

Embraer and OGMA

OGMA was founded in 1918 and is one of the oldest aeronautical companies in Portugal, located in Alverca, in the Lisbon region. For over a century, OGMA has specialized in maintenance, repair, and overhaul (MRO) of aircraft and engines, for both civilian and military clients.

Embraer was created in 1969, with mixed capital status and state control, and was privatized in 1994. Throughout its existence, it has developed and manufactured a range of civilian and military aircraft that have been successful in the aeronautical market.

In 2005, Embraer acquired 65% of OGMA's shares, with the remaining 35% held by the Portuguese State through the holding company Empordef. This partnership strengthened OGMA, integrating it into Embraer's global production chain and expanding its MRO (Maintenance, Repair and Overhaul) capabilities.

OGMA offers maintenance and overhaul services for a wide range of aircraft, including models from Embraer, Airbus, and Lockheed Martin. These services are provided to civilian and military operators worldwide. In addition to MRO, OGMA manufactures aeronautical components, including parts for various Embraer aircraft, contributing to the global supply chain. Embraer and OGMA have an important and complementary presence in the Portuguese aeronautical industry, playing essential roles in both aircraft production and maintenance.

As mentioned earlier, Embraer opened two factories in Évora in 2012, focused on the production of metal components and composite materials. These factories complement OGMA's operations in Alverca, reinforcing Embraer's production and innovation capacity in Portugal.

The relationship between Embraer and OGMA is strategic, allowing the two companies to collaborate on production and maintenance projects. OGMA, with its experience in MRO and manufacturing, works closely with Embraer's factories in Évora to supply components and perform maintenance services for Embraer's global fleet.

The collaboration between Embraer and OGMA has a significant impact on the Portuguese economy, not only in terms of job creation, but also in exports and technological development. The synergy between the two companies also attracts investment and positions

Portugal as an important hub in the global value chain of the aeronautical industry.

The presence of OGMA in Alverca and Embraer's factories in Évora has driven regional development, created highly skilled jobs and promoted technical training in the aeronautical industry.

Embraer and OGMA are involved in several innovation projects, including the development of new aircraft technologies and the use of advanced materials. Collaboration with universities and research centres in Portugal is crucial to maintaining competitiveness in companies in this sector.

Despite the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, which severely affected the aeronautical industry, Embraer and OGMA are positioned to benefit from the sector's recovery. The demand for more efficient and sustainable aircraft may open up new growth opportunities for both companies in Portugal.

Embraer and OGMA have an important and complementary presence in the Portuguese aeronautical industry, playing essential roles in both aircraft production and maintenance.

In Évora, Embraer established two factories when it was created in 2012, as shown in Figure 2, dedicated to the production of metal components and composite materials. These units are vital for the manufacture of parts used in various Embraer aircraft, such as commercial and executive jets.

Embraer has two industrial units in Évora:

Embraer Metallics S.A.: Dedicated to the production of metal structures for aircraft.

Embraer Composites: Focused on the production of components in composite materials, lighter and stronger materials, used in fuselages and other structural parts of aircraft.

In 2022, Embraer transferred the management of its metal structure and composite factories in Évora to the Spanish company Aernnova, as stated by Embraer CEO Francisco Gomes in 2022, "the agreement will allow us to expand occupancy levels at the Évora factories and diversify the customer base, bringing new business opportunities," a strategic partner, therefore.

The transaction aimed to increase production capacity and diversify the customer base of the facilities, while maintaining the continuous supply of components for Embraer's aircraft programs.

This acquisition solidified Aernnova's position as one of the leading global suppliers of aerostructures, and the factories in Évora now operate as critical production centres for both companies, focusing on digital and sustainable innovation in the aeronautical industry (source: The Portugal News, (2022).

In conclusion, Embraer and OGMA play vital roles in the Portuguese aeronautical industry, with operations ranging from component production to aircraft maintenance.

The synergy between Embraer's factories in Évora and OGMA's in Alverca has strengthened Portugal's position as an important aviation hub in Europe. This collaboration not only contributes to regional development and job creation but also places Portugal in a

prominent position in the global value chain of the aeronautical industry.

Portuguese Air Force

The aeronautical and aerospace industry represents a strategic sector for the technological and economic development of any country, characterized by high investments, intensive innovation, and a strong link to national sovereignty. In Portugal, the role of the State has been decisive, both in creating conditions for the formation of industrial clusters and in defining public policies and supporting the internationalization of companies in the sector.

This analysis explores how state intervention influences the competitiveness and sustainability of the Portuguese aeronautical sector, based on academic and institutional evidence. Aeronautical production in Portugal is strongly export-oriented, representing a significant portion of the industrial GDP. Caetano (2012) highlights the need to understand this reality to support political and business decisions:

“To fill the information gap that exists about the Portuguese aeronautical industry, showing the current situation, current projects, and also statistics of the sector in Portugal.” (Caetano, 2012)

The Portuguese state has a strong influence on the aeronautical industry, starting with the skilled workforce; universities are a central pillar of the aerospace and defence ecosystem in Portugal. From north to south of the country, on the coast and inland, we find higher and technical education that decisively contributes to the training and specialization of national talent applied to aeronautics, space, and defence. Caetano, (2012) - The aerospace industry provides a multitude of innovations for other industries and services. Portugal today has the knowledge and experience that allow it to participate in complex international projects in the aerospace industry, of great added value to the country's economy.

The creation of the AED cluster – Aeronautics, Space and Defence, in 2016, marked a watershed moment in the strengthening of the Portuguese aeronautical industry. This cluster, recognized as strategic by the Government, aims to integrate companies, universities, and public entities to foster innovation and competitiveness. As highlighted by Gomes (2024):

“The creation of the Aeronautics, Defence and Space (AED) cluster in 2016 strengthened the sector, increasing employment, turnover and export revenues. The results highlight the importance of governmental and European support, strategic collaboration between companies and the advantages of clusters, such as resource sharing and innovation.” (Gomes, 2024).

The Portuguese Aeronautics, Space and Defence (AED) industry represents 1.4% of the national Gross Domestic Product (GDP), exports 87% of a total turnover of approximately 1.8 billion euros and ensures 18,500 qualified jobs. Nevertheless, General José Cordeiro, head of the AED Cluster Portugal, states that the main objective of the Strategic Plan for 2018/2022 is to “double this value, to 3% of GDP, through the addition of new members”.

Internationalization is a pillar of the competitiveness of the Portuguese aeronautical industry. Companies like OGMA exemplify this process, benefiting from regulatory frameworks and institutional support. According to Pedro (2018), “OGMA was analyzed as a

Portuguese company (...) a pioneer in the Portuguese aeronautical industry and, currently, one of the major players in the international markets of the sector.” (Pedro, 2018)

Despite recent advances, there are historical challenges related to the definition of clear strategies by political power. Ribeiro (2001) identifies that the lack of state guidance was an obstacle to the full development of the sector, “The aerospace industry (...) provides a multitude of innovations for other industries and services. (...) The current impasse in the sector results essentially from a lack of clarification and definition of direction on the part of the political power...” (Ribeiro, 2001)

Currently, there are two projects underway by the Portuguese Air Force academy with significant investment from the Portuguese state, funded by the European Union, with a projected completion date of December 31, 2025. The projects are as follows:

Mobilizing Agenda “New Space Portugal”

The New Space Portugal Mobilizing Agenda aims to boost the Portuguese space industry, promoting national capacity to design, develop and produce complete satellites and payloads, as well as providing high value-added tradable services based on the exploitation of Earth Observation (OT) data. This program, which began in October 2021 and is scheduled to conclude in December 2025, aims for a structural change in the specialization profile of the Portuguese economy, reinforcing the country's position in the European and global space sector.

The main initiatives include:

Development, production, and operation of Very High Resolution and High-Resolution satellite constellations.

Creation of the Digital Planet platform, for the integration and availability of multi-source data with advanced services.

Implementation of complementary services to foster entrepreneurship, education, advanced training, and research in the field of Earth Observation, focusing on the Atlantic and the global context.

“Aero. Next Portugal”

“Aero. Next Portugal” aims to strengthen the national positioning in the aeronautical value chain, consolidating the sector's cluster through the development of complete, complex, and high value-added products. Starting in October 2021 and scheduled for completion in December 2025, this initiative intends to ensure Portugal's capacity in all phases of the cycle — conception, development, industrialization, and commercialization — making the country a relevant decision-making centre and reducing external dependence.

Main objectives: to develop three innovative products:

ARL – LUS2022: light unmanned aircraft (capacity up to 2000 kg, range of 2000 km), prepared for conventional, hybrid, and electric propulsion.

UAS ARX: Unmanned aerial system (class III), with a maximum take-off weight of 800 kg, designed for maritime surveillance missions.

SAAM: Advanced air mobility system (e-VTOL and hybrid e-VTOL), designed for monitoring, surveillance, and transport of urgent cargo (e.g., medical emergencies).

Acquisition of the KC-390

Since the 1970s, the Portuguese Air Force (FAP) operated C-130 Hercules models for logistical transport, but their capacity and technology began to reveal limitations in the face of modern demands. The acquisition of the KC-390 Millennium aircraft by the Portuguese Air Force (FAP) constitutes a strategic decision with significant implications for operational capacity, the national economy, and the development of the Portuguese aeronautical industry. This chapter analyses the motivations for this choice, the technological and industrial benefits, as well as the challenges associated with the implementation of the program, based on academic theses and official documents.

The KC-390 presents itself as a more advanced solution, with greater cargo capacity, speed, and autonomy, fundamental characteristics for FAP operations. In addition to troop and cargo transport, the KC-390 offers flexibility for medical evacuations, disaster support, and aerial refuelling.

The KC-390 program had a direct impact on the Portuguese economy and industrial sector, resulting in the creation of qualified jobs and technology transfer. As Oliveira (2014) points out, "Portugal is not taking full advantage of the opportunity represented by the project, which is marked by a conflict between industrial, defense and economic perspectives. [...] ultimately, it contributed to improving the country's technological credibility."

Despite the challenges identified by Oliveira (2014), the project allowed the national industry to participate in advanced engineering phases, with more than 650,000 engineering hours carried out in Portugal and more than 350 highly qualified jobs created.

Airbus

Airbus has strengthened its presence in Portugal with the inauguration of important production facilities and specialized services. In 2022, the company opened the Airbus Atlantic factory in Santo Tirso, in northern Portugal, after an investment of around 40 million euros. This unit, which began construction in 2020, occupies 20,000 square meters and is expected to employ up to 250 workers, who will produce essential components for the Airbus A320 and A350 aircraft families. Focusing on parts such as seats and other aerostructures, the factory is part of a strategy to integrate Portugal into Airbus' global production ecosystem, especially in the area of cutting-edge technologies for the aeronautical sector (Aeronautical magazine space and defense "The sky may not be the limit", June 2024)

In addition to the factory in Santo Tirso, Airbus expanded its Global Service Centre in Lisbon, which serves areas such as finance, sales, engineering and human resources. This centre, located in Parque das Nações, aims to employ up to 1200 people by 2026, being a central piece in Airbus' global support for commercial and administrative operations.

Combined, these investments reinforce Portugal's role as a strategic hub for the development of the aeronautical industry, contributing to the creation of specialized jobs and the strengthening of the country's technological infrastructure.

It recently employs more than 1000 workers between the two centres (Coimbra and Lisbon), exceeding the initial expectations of 800 people by 2025, now making the target

1200 by 2025.

These investments reflect not only Airbus' commitment to Portugal, but also a significant economic impact, including the creation of skilled jobs and growth in industrial production, aligned with the national strategy for the development of the aeronautical sector.

Airbus works with several Portuguese companies for the production of aeronautical components. These partnerships are crucial to Airbus' global supply chain, with Portuguese companies providing parts and subcomponents for various aircraft.

The main impacts of Airbus in Portugal are as follows:

Employment and Regional Development: Airbus' activities in Portugal, together with its partners, have generated skilled jobs in areas such as engineering and manufacturing. These activities have boosted economic development in regions such as Lisbon, Évora, and Oporto.

Technology Transfer: Collaboration with Airbus has facilitated the transfer of advanced technology to Portugal, strengthening the capabilities of Portuguese companies in the aeronautical sector and contributing to global competitiveness.

Exports: Portuguese companies involved in the Airbus supply chain play an important role in exports, supplying components and services for aircraft that are marketed globally.

Sustainability and Innovation: Airbus is investing in new technologies to reduce carbon emissions, such as the development of hydrogen-powered aircraft. Portugal, through its partnerships with Airbus, can benefit from these advances, participating in innovation projects aimed at a more sustainable future in aviation.

Airbus has considerable influence in the aviation sector in Portugal, not only through its operations but also through strategic partnerships with local companies. These collaborations are fundamental to the development of the industry, providing jobs, innovation, and economic growth. The continuation of this cooperation is essential to maintain Portugal as a relevant player in the global aviation industry, especially as Airbus advances with new technologies and sustainable practices.

Airbus Atlantic

The Airbus Atlantic plant in Porto is one of the company's strategic facilities, focused on the production of structural components for aircraft, including fuselages, wings, and other critical parts. This unit is part of the global Airbus Atlantic network, which is dedicated to the manufacture of high-tech aeronautical structures. According to Cedric Gautier (CEO) Airbus Atlantic Group (quoted in AICEP), "Due to its strategic location, skilled workforce, and hospitality, Portugal is an attractive destination for developing the aerospace sector." Portugal is an attractive country for Airbus, with a skilled and inexpensive workforce, its climate, and strategic location. It is the closest country by sea to the American continent and has great proximity not only to strategic suppliers but also to the main Airbus factories and hangars (Madrid and Toulouse).

The main specialization of the Porto unit is particularly involved in the production of composite materials and other advanced technologies that are essential for the construction of modern and efficient aircraft. These components are used in various Airbus aircraft,

including commercial jets and military aircraft. They are then shipped to the factory in Madrid or directly to Toulouse, where the FAL (Final Assembly Line) is located.

Airbus Atlantic Portugal announced on July 31, 2024, that it will increase the area of its factory in Santo Tirso by 5,500 square meters, corresponding to 30% of the industrial area, which should be operational in the first quarter of 2026. With this expansion, it is expected that at least 50 more professionals will be hired by the end of 2025, and many more until the expansion is complete and everything is operational.

According to the company, the expansion "aims to respond to the significant growth of Airbus programs, given that Airbus Atlantic Portugal currently produces fuselage sections for the Airbus A320 and A350 families."

The company plans to further expand its operations in Portugal in the coming years, with the goal of the country representing a significant part of the production of parts delivered to the main Airbus factory in France.

Airbus GBS (Global Business Services)

Airbus GBS (Global Business Services) is an Airbus unit dedicated to providing global business services, with a significant presence in Portugal. This center plays a key role in managing and optimizing Airbus's internal processes, supporting various divisions of the company worldwide.

Location: Airbus GBS established one of its main centres in Lisbon and Coimbra, Portugal. These centres were inaugurated in 2016 as part of Airbus's strategy to centralize and optimize its business support services.

Purpose: The Airbus GBS in Lisbon was created to improve the efficiency and quality of support services for Airbus operations. These functions include areas such as finance, human resources, purchasing, information technology (IT), and project management.

Functions: The Lisbon unit provides financial management, accounting, purchasing support, IT, and other administrative services to the various Airbus divisions globally.

The deployment of Airbus GBS in Lisbon has generated hundreds of jobs, mainly in areas such as finance, process management, and IT. This centre attracts qualified professionals and contributes to the economic development of the region.

The presence of Airbus GBS in Portugal allows workers to develop skills in critical areas of business management and technology, providing opportunities for continuous training and development.

Thus, Airbus strengthens the shared services sector in Portugal, creating stable and highly specialized jobs that reinforce the development of the Portuguese technology sector.

With the growing need for digitalization and automation, Airbus GBS in Lisbon plans to expand into new areas, including data analytics and artificial intelligence, areas that should further strengthen the efficiency and agility of Airbus' global operations. "Portugal, with its pool of competitive talent, outstanding quality, capacity and cost advantages, becomes an obvious partner for Airbus."

This service centre is also expected to lead in the implementation of predictive analytics tools to improve decision-making and in the automation of routine processes,

boosting productivity across various divisions.

UAS and UAVs (drone sector, unmanned aircraft)

With the advent of unmanned aircraft and their integration into airspace, a recent study valued the global UAS market (commercial and personal) at approximately US\$22 billion in 2020, and expected to triple by 2030 (Bachal & Mutreja, 2021; Brand essence Market Research and Consulting Pvt Ltd, 2021; Research and Markets, 2022), suggesting a growth in the use of these devices in global airspace. The global UAS market is growing exponentially, with a significant increase in market value projected, rising from \$11 billion in 2022 to \$29 billion in 2027 (ICAO. (2020). Emerging Aviation Issues — Increased use of unmanned aerial systems (UAS) and remotely piloted aircraft systems (RPAS)

According to the data, the outlook is positive and growing. While initially the use of UAS was restricted to military use, currently, the application of UAS is also civilian and quite diversified. In the civilian sphere, studies have been conducted on the use of UAS in travel, public services, logistics deliveries, and agriculture, among others (Chew et al., 2020; Kugler, 2019; Muñoz et al., 2019; Skorobogatov et al., 2020). And recently, UAS have been used in the decontamination of areas affected by COVID-19, in the surveillance of public spaces and for monitoring areas by the Security Forces and Services (FSS) in Hungary.

In 2024, the drone market size is expected to reach 35.28 billion, and this value is expected to double in 2029.

With this growth in UAS worldwide, incidents involving UAS have also increased.

Within Portugal, ANAC (National Civil Aviation Authority) is responsible for administering tests and certifying UAV pilots. This certification is viable and operational throughout the European airspace, which is controlled by EASA.

ANAC provides almost all the necessary information for using UAS on its website, and also offers an application called "Voa na Boa" that allows users (in mainland Portugal) to know under what conditions they can fly their UAV, identify their location and the different areas, namely, free flight areas, restricted flight areas, flight subject to authorization, military jurisdiction areas and prohibited flight areas (ANAC, 2020).

However, this system is isolated, does not interact with different UAV operators or other systems, falling short of the North American LAANC system. An international networked system would be ideal for the future, connecting all UAV pilots and allowing for easier security and monitoring by the legal authorities of each airspace.

Associated with LAANC, UAS operators have access to an online tool, controlled areas and their respective altitudes where they can fly and submit the UAV flight authorization request.

With regard to UAS legislation, Portugal, as a member of the EU, has applied European regulations, thus ensuring "...mutual recognition between the Member States of the European Union of authorizations, certificates, training and theoretical competence of remote pilots..." (ANAC, n.d.).

UAVision and the Ogassa OGS-42

UAVision Aeronautics was created and has been developing UAS systems since

2005. It is a Portuguese company headquartered in the Leiria district.

With over 18 years of experience in the development of unmanned aerial vehicles and subsystems, it initially focused on the development and manufacture of communication systems. (according to the official UAVision website)

UAVision offers a variety of UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) platforms, including fixed-wing and multi-engine drones. These systems are designed to operate in different environments and meet the needs of various sectors, such as defense, security and surveillance, border control, and infrastructure and environmental monitoring. (UAVision official website)

UAVision collaborates with various national and international organizations to develop innovative solutions, having participated in European programs such as Horizon 2020. The company invests significantly in Research and Development (R&D), approximately 30% (according to the UAVision official website), to improve the capabilities of its products, including autonomous navigation systems, payload integration (such as cameras and sensors), and improvements in the endurance and range of UAVs.

The development of the UAS sector in Portugal generates new economic and technological opportunities. UAVision, by working on national and international projects, puts Portugal on the map of technological innovation for drone production, contributing to job creation and the training of skilled labour in areas such as robotics, data analysis and aeronautical engineering, with universities and research centres, promoting innovation and the development of new materials and software for UAS control systems.

Portugal uses the Ogassa OGS-42 UAS in its armed forces, mainly for surveillance and control, through thermal cameras the Portuguese Air Force monitors fires in high-risk areas.

TEKEVER

Tekever is a Portuguese high-tech company specializing in the development of drones (UAVs) and artificial intelligence solutions applied to maritime surveillance, defense, and security. Founded in 2001, Tekever has become one of the leading European references in unmanned aircraft.

Tekever produces a range of unmanned aerial systems (UAS), including:

AR3 – Lightweight, portable drone with vertical take-off/landing capabilities, ideal for operations in difficult terrain.

AR4 – Short-range micro-drone, mainly used for rapid reconnaissance.

AR5 – Medium and long-range tactical drone with radar and satellite communications (SATCOM), used for maritime surveillance and beyond-line-of-sight (BRLOS) operations.

All drones feature TEKEVER ATLAS, an AI-based platform that analyses and transmits data in real time to support decision-making.

3. Evolution of the Portuguese Economy (2014-2024)

After the economic crisis of 2008-2013 and the intervention of the Troika, Portugal

began a recovery process, marked by an increase in GDP and a significant reduction in unemployment. During this period, the aeronautical industry stood out as a strategic sector. Portugal attracted foreign investment to the aeronautical industry sector, especially with the installation of Embraer units in Évora and the growth of OGMA's operations in Alverca, becoming important hubs for the production and maintenance of aeronautical components.

The aeronautical industry in Portugal has consolidated itself as a strategic sector for the country's economic development, contributing to the export of high technology, the creation of qualified jobs, and the attraction of foreign direct investment.

In 2016, AED Cluster Portugal was created, which is the Portuguese Cluster for the Aeronautics, Space and defence Industries.

The strategic objectives of AED Cluster Portugal fall within four main pillars: Financing and Regulation; People and Skills; Innovation and Value; Markets and Opportunities – with the clear mission of promoting the advancement and consolidation of Portugal as an international reference in the global Aeronautics, Space and Defense markets.

Over time, it has experienced a gradual increase in membership and revenue, representing 1.4% of the national gross domestic product (GDP) in 2019. Although its growth in relation to GDP for 2024 is not as expected in 2019, it still has a significant influence on the Portuguese economy. According to AED Cluster Portugal, there are more than 150 members among R&D centres, Industry and systems, and ICT members of the cluster, generating around 18,500 jobs in Portugal in the sector, with a turnover of 1.72 billion.

In the aeronautics, space and defence sectors, the systems developed are generally complex and require substantial investments. Therefore, "According to Neves, J. (2024, October). The sky may not be the limit in an interview)) the president of AED Cluster Portugal considers that the best option is to promote collaborative work between various entities. "We already have good examples of projects, including research and development, created by ten or twenty companies in conjunction with the scientific and technological system," the support of AICEP in promoting Portugal abroad and attracting investment has also been important. "This is critical for the sector and its growth," he says, also highlighting the importance of creating and retaining talent that has contributed to the sector's success.

The cluster brings together a wide variety of companies, from those that make cutting tools associated with the aeronautical production sector to those that develop embedded systems in satellites. "There are very interesting business models in the area of aerostructures, and this can be seen in the commitment of international players who have come to Portugal," says Rui Santos.

"Also in the maintenance area, several SMEs dedicated to the manufacture of equipment are beginning to appear." The Airbus factory in Santo Tirso or The Aernnova plant in Évora is one example. "Parts of considerable size are already being manufactured in Portugal, which is also a game changer, unlike what was happening 15 years ago," adds José Neves.

If we take inflation into account, we can better identify the actual GDP growth in Portugal and identify the true rate of economic growth in the country, where it can be concluded that Covid-19 had a major impact on economic growth, which fell by about 8.2%.

In 2021 and 2022 there was significant economic growth due to strong government investment in various sectors, but in 2023 it fell again, although positive and representing an increase in the economy, its percentage is lower than in the previous 2 years.

Gross Value Added (GVA), although it mentions sectors such as the metallurgical industry, transformation and manufacturing of plastic and non-metallic mineral products, is directly linked to the aeronautical industry. The production of structural components for aircraft (fuselages, wings, engine parts) depends heavily on advanced metallurgical capabilities.

The manufacturing industry involves manufacturing and assembly processes that are crucial in the production of aircraft and subcomponents. The stability of this branch suggests installed capacity but may also indicate a need for innovation to increase competitiveness in supplying companies such as Embraer, OGMA or Airbus.

The plastic and non-metallic mineral products branch includes composite materials, high-performance plastics and technical ceramics, widely used in aviation to reduce weight and increase strength. The drop in 2022 and the rapid recovery in 2023 may reflect supply disruptions or adjustments in demand linked to the resumption of aeronautical production post-pandemic.

Between 2014 and 2023, there was a relatively stable evolution in the three activities analysed, with moderate variations throughout the period. In general, the metallurgical and plastic products sectors proved to be more dynamic, while the manufacturing industry remained with modest and stable growth.

Overall, the evolution of GVA in these three branches suggests that Portugal has complementary industrial sectors capable of sustaining the growth of the aeronautical industry, especially if there is a focus on technological innovation, international certifications and integration into global value chains.

The evolution of the workforce employed in companies in two sectors, Manufacturing (brown line) and Administrative Activities (green line), during the period 2014-2023.

The manufacturing industry experienced continuous growth between 2014 and 2019 (from approximately 650,000 to 750,000). In 2020 there was a decrease (approximately 720,000), possibly associated with the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

After that, there was a slow recovery, reaching approximately 750,000 in 2023. Administrative activities experienced more pronounced growth than manufacturing, but also saw a decrease in 2020, although the recovery was stronger. Although the aeronautical industry is only a niche within these two sectors, it still had some impact, mainly with OGMA with the KC-390 and Airbus GBS, primarily in administrative activities. If the current trend continues, it is possible that Administrative Activities will continue to approach the Manufacturing Industry and may even surpass it in the coming years.

According to the National Institute of Statistics (INE, 2022), the Portuguese aeronautical industry contributes significantly to the national GDP and represents one of the main export sectors, especially in the areas of composite materials and maintenance and repair services (INE, 2022).

The main export markets in the aeronautical industry in Portugal were Brazil (35.9%),

USA (17.9%), France (16.2%), Ireland (15.3%), Switzerland (5.6%) weight on total exports. Brazil and France mainly due to the great influence of Airbus and Embraer.

According to AICEP (2022), Portugal's agency for foreign investment, several multinationals have invested in Portugal in recent years, such as Aernnova, Lauak, Mecachrome or Airbus Atlantic. This fact can be attributed to the highly qualified human resources existing in Portugal, their proficiency in English and their vast experience in engineering as well as the low cost of workers compared to other European countries. In addition, the existence of R&D centres and high-quality suppliers further reinforces Portugal's attractiveness to these multinational organizations.

According to SABI, the Top 5 international companies with the highest turnover (2021), the main investors in the aeronautical industry in Portugal are Airbus, OGMA, and Aeronova.

Companies like OGMA collaborate on Research & Development (R&D) projects in partnership with local universities and research centres, promoting innovation in the sector and strengthening the industry's international competitiveness.

According to a study by Banco do Brazil (2021), the impact of the aeronautical industry on the labour market is remarkable, generating highly specialized jobs that require technical and professional training in engineering and advanced manufacturing (Banco do Brazil, 2021).

In addition, Portugal offers world-class engineering schools and universities equipped with comprehensive workforce qualification programs specifically designed for the aeronautical and aerospace sector.

The Impact of COVID-19 on the Aeronautical Industry

The COVID-19 pandemic imposed serious challenges on the global economy, and the aeronautical sector was one of the most affected due to flight suspensions and supply chain disruptions. In Portugal, companies like TAP Air Portugal faced significant financial difficulties, requiring government support.

However, the industry showed resilience, with companies like OGMA implementing digitalization strategies and new health and safety protocols to maintain operations. The aeronautical industry in Portugal underwent profound changes due to the COVID-19 pandemic, marked by a sharp reduction in demand for air travel and the weakening of global supply chains.

The sector had to deal with staff reductions as demand for new projects and maintenance decreased drastically. The Bank of Portugal (2021) highlights that the aeronautical industry was one of the most affected in terms of unemployment and wage cuts.

Government financial support programs and mitigation measures, such as simplified layoff schemes, were implemented to lessen the effects of the crisis, but even so, many workers were laid off.

Post-COVID-19

The recovery of the aviation industry in Portugal in the post-COVID-19 period has been marked by the gradual return of operations, with a strategic adaptation focused on sustainability, technological innovation, and health safety.

After the most critical phase of the pandemic, the sector has been working to face new challenges, such as the digitization of processes, the recovery of consumer confidence, and the reduction of the carbon footprint. Companies such as TAP Air Portugal, OGMA, and Aernnova have sought to align their operations with global trends and position themselves competitively.

The economic recovery in Portugal after the health crisis has proven to be a stage of readjustment in multiple sectors, and aviation, being a sector of great economic impact and employment, still faces the challenge of fully stabilizing and adapting to new expectations of resilience and safety, as indicated by studies on the economic impact of the pandemic in Portugal. (Nuno Jalali, Impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic in Portugal 2022)

The recovery of the aeronautical sector has a positive impact on the Portuguese economy, contributing to the creation of skilled jobs and stimulating economic growth through exports and maintenance and engineering services.

Projections for the Portuguese Economy (2025-2027)

According to the Bank of Portugal (2025), until 2027, the Portuguese economy will continue to grow at a rate higher than that of the euro area. Growth will be more balanced, supported by investment and exports and not so much by consumption. Employment will increase more slowly and unemployment will remain low.

The Portuguese economy should continue to grow in the coming years, although at a more moderate pace from 2027 onwards, due to the end of the Recovery and Resilience Plan. Short-term growth will be supported by more favourable financial conditions, increased external demand and more intensive use of European funds.

Consumption and investment may benefit from greater confidence but depend on a reduction in internal and external uncertainty. Increased employment and stabilization of the unemployment rate are expected, as well as a fall in inflation to values close to the target. The economy should maintain above-average performance in the euro area, with a virtually zero inflation differential. (Bank of Portugal, 2025).

Human Resources and Educational Institutions (Portugal)

Portugal has several higher education institutions offering specialized courses in aeronautical and aerospace engineering, including the Instituto Superior Técnico, the University of Beira Interior, the Instituto Universitário Atlântica, and the University of Minho, among others, where highly qualified professionals are trained, essential for the sustained growth of the sector.

In the area of management and aeronautical sciences, Portugal also has several specialized higher education courses in Management and Aeronautical Sciences, namely the Lusófona University of Lisbon, the Instituto Superior de Educação e Ciências (ISEC Lisboa), and Atlântica – Instituto Universitário.

These training programs aim to prepare qualified professionals to work in the areas of airport management, air transport operations, maintenance, planning, and aeronautical safety. The contribution of these institutions is essential for the sustained development of the aviation sector in Portugal, promoting innovation and operational efficiency.

4. Materials and Methods

The methodology used in this research was divided into 2 parts:

Qualitative:

A literature review on the impact that the aeronautical industry has had on the Portuguese economy in recent years, focusing on the companies with the greatest impact in the last ten years and which are expected to have a significant impact on the Portuguese economy in the future.

Quantitative:

Quantitative research is that which generates numerical or statistical results (Corbin & Strauss, 2015), that is, data that can be measured or counted.

For Bell (2008), “quantitative researchers collect facts and study the relationship between them”, in this study based on a random sample.

To understand and obtain statistical data, research was conducted to better understand the impact of technological innovation on the sector, the profile of employees, expectations, and perceptions about the future of the industry.

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards of confidentiality and data protection, guaranteeing the privacy of all those involved.

Figure 1 – Conceptual Framework

Source: Performed by the Research Study team

Research is a survey that allows one to know the opinion of a population about a given subject, based on a representative sample of that population. (Étienne et al., 1998: 279)

The survey was open to professionals in the aeronautical sector in Portugal from October 30 to March 24, 2025, and was primarily aimed at employees of Airbus and the Portuguese Air Force. "What allows us to say that a survey leads to more credible results is that the logic behind the use of a sample is to concentrate efforts to reduce, not each type of error individually, but both types of error [sampling errors and non-sampling errors] together." (Vicente et al., 1996).

This research aims to:

Identify and classify the age and academic levels of professionals in the sector. Data analysis allows for the rapid classification of participants based on demographic and professional characteristics.

It is a common practice in research methodology, as explored by Fowler (2014), who discusses the impact of demographic questions on understanding the profile of respondents and on the analysis of subgroups within the study.

For an expected population of 200, only 50 are the final sample.

Two interviews were also conducted at Airbus GBS:

1. Interview with Ana Soares, Head of People and Culture HR, Airbus GBS.
2. Interview with Maria Madalena De Sá, Head of Integrated Finance, Director of Public Affairs.

Their perception of the relevance of the Aeronautical industry in the Brazilian economy, future perspectives on the industry, and general opinion on the future of UAVs and UASs.

5. Results and Discussion

Within the sample obtained, regarding demographic data, the majority of professionals in the aeronautics field in Portugal are men, aged between 18 and 35 years old. This indicates that Portugal has a young and qualified workforce, a good sign for the future of the sector in the country. The vast majority also have a higher academic level.

The professionals in this sample are practically divided between military and private aeronautics. The sample shows that a large percentage perform functions in engineering and finance departments.

Operations and component manufacturing were mostly carried out by members of the Portuguese Air Force, a large part of whom perform functions in air defence and security operations. A large percentage of respondents are young people up to 35 years old with up to 5 years of experience in the field, demonstrating that Portugal currently has young professionals in this area.

With the significant growth of companies in the aeronautics sector in Portugal, such as Airbus through GBS in the last 5 years, the largest percentage of experience in the aeronautics field is 3 to 5 years.

The aeronautics sector requires companies to operate in both international and national markets, which also reveals the strong support from the Portuguese state in this industry.

Graph 1 – Relevant Data of the Research Study

Source: Study authors observation

We can conclude that the sector is strongly oriented towards maintenance and digitalization services, with less focus on the production of traditional components, signalling that pure design and traditional production are less central.

Maintenance is the most representative area, mentioned by 72% of respondents (36 responses), reinforcing the dominant role of MRO (Maintenance, Repair and Overhaul) activities in Portugal.

The maintenance area is the central area in Portugal, complemented by technological activities and services. The business link is mainly with European manufacturers (Airbus), with little integration with the USA (Boeing). Embraer's presence in Portugal is also noteworthy.

State intervention is considered essential, especially in the military sector, but also in the private/civilian sector, to sustain growth and ensure international competitiveness.

The vast majority (98%) believe that the State should intervene and support the sector.

This result shows that professionals recognize the importance of public investment, not only for maintaining the military fleet and strengthening national defence, but also for supporting the civil and private sectors, ensuring competitiveness and growth.

Thus, the Portuguese aeronautical sector is seen by its professionals as small in size, but highly strategic, with high potential for sustained growth through innovation, international partnerships, and supportive public policies. All respondents consider the sector strategic for the country.

Regarding the degree of relevance of factors for the growth of the sector in Portugal, financial support is considered relevant by a large part of the respondents (Important and Very important), although there is some weight in the "Not very important" category.

This suggests that, for some professionals, growth depends not only on financial

incentives, but also on organizational and technological structure.

6. Conclusion of the results obtained

The analysis of the results obtained through the survey shows a generally positive perception regarding the development and relevance of the aeronautical industry in Portugal. Most participants attribute high importance to factors such as state financial support, research laboratories, and associations for the development of the sector, elements considered crucial to promoting competitiveness and national economic growth.

Another relevant aspect is related to the need for professional adaptation. Most respondents recognize that the evolution of technology will imply significant changes in the labour market, requiring retraining and continuous training to adapt skills to the new demands of the sector.

However, the survey data reveal a concern about the shortage of qualified engineers and technicians, which may be an obstacle to the sustained growth of the national aeronautical industry.

This factor reinforces the need for investment in specialized training programs and public policies aimed at technical training, thus ensuring the availability of adequate human resources.

Table 1 – Correlation Matrix

Correlation Matrix		VAR(1)	VAR(2)	VAR(3)	VAR(4)	VAR(5)	VAR(6)
International (1)	R- Pearson	---					
	N	---					
	p - value	---					
Associations (2)	R- Pearson	0,589	---				
	N	50	---				
	p - value	0,0001	---				
Research (3)	R- Pearson	0,735	0,855	---			
	N	50	50	---			
	p - value	0,0001	0,0001	---			
Financial (4)	R- Pearson	0,503	0,553	0,657	---		
	N	50	50	50	---		
	p - value	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	---		
State (5)	R- Pearson	0,503	0,771	0,765	0,629	---	
	N	50	50	50	50	---	
	p - value	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	0,0001	---	
Technology (6)	R- Pearson	-0,062	-0,025	-0,055	-0,020	-0,009	---
	N	50	50	50	50	50	---
	p - value	0,6318	0,8458	0,6689	0,8747	0,9468	---

Source: Done by the authors based on the study collected data

In summary, the results indicate that a focus on innovation, professional qualification, and integration into international programs is considered essential to consolidate Portugal's position in the aeronautical value chain and boost its competitiveness in a constantly evolving global market.

Strategic Recommendations Based on Results:

Strengthening Specialized Training: Develop educational and advanced training programs in aeronautical engineering and emerging technologies, focusing on UAVs and advanced air mobility.

Support for Research and Development: Create tax and financial incentives for companies and research centres that invest in technological innovation in the aeronautical sector.

Promotion of Clusters and Collaborative Networks: Enhance partnerships between universities, companies, and government entities to strengthen the national value chain.

Integration into International Projects: Ensure active participation in European and global initiatives, increasing the visibility and competitiveness of Portuguese companies.

Professional Retraining Programs: Implement labour adaptation policies to prepare professionals for the changes resulting from digitalization and automation in the sector.

Airbus GBS Interviews as final note

Interview with Ana Soares, Head of People and Culture, HR at Airbus GBS:

The interview highlights an optimistic vision for the future of the aeronautical industry in Portugal, positioning the country as a strategic hub of high added value, based on innovation, co-creation, and knowledge production.

Airbus' Global Business Services (GBS) in Lisbon is presented as a central element of this transformation, evolving from an operational role to a strategic function of corporate intelligence.

The interviewee's statement emphasizes talent as the main factor of competitiveness, valuing not only technical skills but also behavioural skills, such as collaboration, critical thinking, and a focus on continuous improvement.

Digital fluency, adaptive leadership, and the ability to co-create value are identified as key competencies for the future of the sector, reflecting the need to adapt to highly complex contexts and accelerated digital transformation.

Finally, the interview highlights the importance of the articulation between industry and educational institutions, as well as the existence of structured pipelines for the integration of young talent, considered essential to guarantee the sustainability and competitiveness of the aeronautical industry in Brazil.

Interview with Maria Madalena De Sá, Head of Integrated Finance, Director of Public Affairs:

The interview highlights Portugal as an attractive destination for investment by Airbus and other companies in the aeronautical sector, mainly due to the quality of available talent, the technical skills of professionals, high fluency in English, and workforce flexibility. Furthermore, structural factors such as economic, social, and political stability, as well as the country's strategic geopolitical location, are also important.

Airbus's role in boosting the national aeronautical sector is evidenced by continuous investment in people, infrastructure, and training, reflected in the high level of qualification of

GBS employees and the company's presence throughout the national territory.

Also noteworthy is the indirect economic impact, materialized in collaboration with national suppliers and in strategic partnerships aimed at strengthening engineering and technological development in Portugal.

Finally, the interviewee highlights the importance of Airbus GBS in Portugal as a strategic element supporting the company's global growth, through the centralization of support functions, allowing industrial units to focus on their core business.

This approach reinforces GBS's contribution to value creation and Airbus's strategic positioning in the international context.

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